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CROSSING COMMUNITY BOUNDARIES: CENTRAL CITY VERSUS SUBURBAN ATTENDANCE OF THE PERFORMING ARTS

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Abstract

This case study of performing arts attendance in the Twin Cities (United States) in the early 2000s explores individual characteristics associated with the willingness to cross from city to suburb or from suburb to city for cultural offerings. It draws on data collected from telephone surveys with residents regarding their attendance behaviors and attitudes toward the performing arts. We learn that most boundary crossing occurs in the direction from suburb to city, likely due to the fact that most flagship cultural offerings are located in the central cities. Suburban residents who travel to the central city tend to have higher household incomes, but are not otherwise distinguishable by age or level of education. These boundary crossers seek a broad range of performance offerings, including dance, theatre, and live classical music. Suburbanites are not deterred by concerns about safety, even as city dwellers attend performing arts in the suburbs due to safety concerns. The cost effectiveness of urban offerings may be a draw for suburban audiences, as these suburban boundary crossers voice concerns about the price of attendance.

Keywords: performing arts, attendance, urban, suburban, mobility

Introduction:

Many suburban areas of metropolitan communities in the United States are no longer underdeveloped residential areas that serve as bedrooms for urban commuters and havens from the ills of the central city. While many suburban residents do commute into their central cities for work, their home communities have become increasingly established with their own services, commerce, industry, entertainment, and social problems.

While the issues described in the following paper represent one metropolitan area at one point in time, it is a community and point in time where the question about equity of resources between central cities and suburbs took center stage. In 2001, the established suburbs of the Minneapolis-St. Paul metropolitan area convened and actively questioned why community resources routinely flowed to the performing arts institutions in the central cities rather than to the range of new arts organizations in the surrounding suburbs. The question spurred considerable reflection among arts organizations and funders alike on the topic of suburban development and prevailing biases toward the central city institutions. That the central city housed the more developed arts organizations was not in question. The purpose of the reflection was to consciously acknowledge how a lack of institutional focus on suburban arts organizations and presenters stunted the growth of the professional performing arts in suburbs that increasingly developed their own identities. Twin Cities funders developed a report, *A New Angle: Arts Development in the Suburbs* (Bye, 2002), to codify their commitment to suburban arts organizations.

The purpose of the current research is to pose an empirical snapshot of how residents of the Minneapolis-St. Paul metropolitan area experienced the performing arts in their central cities and surrounding suburbs at that time. It considers the forces that encourage residents of the central counties to attend outside of the downtown area. It also considers the factors that led residents of suburb-dominated surrounding counties to forego their local offerings and attend performing arts events in the central cities. In short, the work attempts to shed light on the central city vs. suburbs issue by considering who crosses community boundaries to attend the performing arts, and why they do so.

The Twin Cities

The “Twin Cities” of Minneapolis and St. Paul are centered in twin counties that constitute the metropolitan centers of the state of Minnesota. Hennepin and Ramsey Counties were home to over 1.6 million people in 2000. However, a substantial and increasing proportion of the metropolitan population reside in five counties, Dakota, Anoka, Washington, Scott, and

Carver, which surround the central counties.¹ These five counties claimed just over 1 million people at the turn of the century. Hennepin and Ramsey Counties grew by 7 percent between the 1990 and 2000 censuses, while the suburban counties grew by 32 percent.

As might be expected, the central county and suburban populations were different in some potentially important ways. The suburban counties had more individuals under 18 years old (30 percent vs. 25 percent) and fewer individuals over the age of 65 (7 percent vs. 11 percent). The suburban counties had a larger majority white population, 93 percent vs. 80 percent in the central counties. The average suburban household had a higher income, with a median of over \$60,000 versus a median of less than \$50,000 in Hennepin and Ramsey Counties. This difference is reflected in the homeownership in 2000 as well, with 82 percent of suburban households living in owned residences and only 65 percent of central county residents being able to make the same claim.

However, as now, commerce, entertainment, and culture were headquartered in the central cities. A large number of suburban residents commuted into the city to work, to play, and to attend sporting and arts events. Major commuter arteries made the cities accessible to suburbanites. The average commute time for residents in the surrounding counties was only slightly longer (25 minutes) than the commute time for residents of the central counties (22 minutes).

While work may be the main reason that many area residents travel downtown, the cities offer a variety of reasons why area residents may choose to stay downtown or to make a special trip on non-work days. The Twin Cities offers their residents professional baseball, football, hockey, and men's and women's basketball. They offer the nightlife, university life, restaurants, and coffee klatches typical of any major city in the United States. The central city community of Bloomington offers residents and tourists the largest shopping complex in the United States. Most important to the work discussed in this paper, the central cities are the home to the cities' major performing arts organizations. In 2000, 130 nonprofit performing arts organizations filed their annual Form 990 with the IRS, including 7 performing arts centers and schools, 16 dance

¹ Hennepin County extends into suburban and exurban areas of the metropolitan area, while Ramsey County rather more contains St. Paul and parts of its closest-in suburbs. The five "suburban" counties in this study do not fully ring Hennepin and Ramsey Counties because Hennepin County itself extends into suburban areas. Ideally, to present a more consistent analysis, Hennepin County could be cut into its constituent central city and suburban parts. However, to simplify analysis, and because of data limitations, we treat all of Hennepin County as part of the central city.

organizations, 40 theatrical organizations, 43 instrumental and choral music organizations, and 24 other kinds of performing arts entities. The Twin Cities are home to theatre and orchestra organizations with budgets of over \$10 million a year.

In contrast, the suburban communities in the surrounding counties radiate the docility of residential life. Sporting events are limited to secondary and high school contests, and the nightlife and restaurants are more typical of those of much smaller communities. In 2000, only 14 nonprofit performing arts organizations had addresses in the five suburban counties. Of these 14, only 4 had annual expenditures of \$100,000 or more, and none spent as much as \$200,000. This number almost certainly undercounts the number of performing arts organizations that operated in the region, including small unincorporated troupes and those that function under the auspices of schools, churches, and local government. The suburbs may also be home to more amateur performing arts organizations – choirs, bands, and community theatre groups whose mission is to provide performing arts opportunities for their local residents rather than to present professional performing arts. Nonetheless, the proportion of undercounted in the suburban counties is likely to be roughly similar to the proportion undercounted in the central cities, so these numbers illustrate the disparity and concentration of professional performing arts activities in Hennepin and Ramsey Counties.

Research Question and Hypotheses:

The central Twin Cities function in a symbiotic relationship with their outlying suburbs where most of their workers spend most of their non-working hours. World-class performing arts performances are one reason why suburban dwellers might choose to make a special trip into or spend more time in the central cities. On the other hand, the emerging manifestations of the performing arts in the suburban counties may provide inner-city arts aficionados the reason to leave the central cities and explore the communities that house a large number of citizens of the metropolitan area. The analyses presented in this paper are driven by our desire to understand the factors associated with individuals who choose to migrate to or from the central cities in order to attend performing arts events.

We develop four different rationales for why people might migrate across community boundaries to attend performing arts performances. First, as is typical in studies of performing arts attendance, we posit that an individual's age, education level, and household income level will influence attendance patterns across community boundaries. We expect that younger, more educated, and higher income city dwellers will be more likely to travel to the suburbs to consort with those whom they resemble on these demographic characteristics. However, we also expect that the more educated and higher income suburbanites will be those who travel into the city for performances. This hypothesis comes from our observation that attendance in the Twin Cities is generally associated with higher education and income levels (identifying reference), which suggests that individuals with these characteristics are most likely to seek the performances from the established entities in the central cities.

Second, we expect that an individual's overall attendance habits at performing arts events will influence their desire to travel across community boundaries to attend particular performances. Since most of the established entities are in the central cities, we expect that suburbanites who are attenders of dance, theatre, orchestra, opera, and other performing arts forms will be among those who say they travel into Hennepin and Ramsey Counties to see performing arts performances. In contrast, given the relatively fewer cultural offerings in the suburban counties, we do not expect that overall attendance will influence central city dwellers' decisions to cross into suburban counties to sample their cultural offerings.

Third, we hypothesize that an individual's attitudes about the performing arts and the extent of their personal participation in arts activities will influence their desire to seek performing arts performances across community boundaries. That is, we expect that positive attitudes and active personal participation will be associated with boundary crossing, regardless of whether an individual is a city dweller seeking performances outside the central city or a suburbanite seeking the diversity and quality of performances nearer the downtowns.

Fourth, we believe that an individual's perceived barriers to attendance will influence their willingness to travel across community boundaries. We consider three different kinds of barriers: cost of tickets, transportation, and their sense of safety or familiarity with the neighborhoods that house performing arts organizations. We expect that suburbanites who are concerned about cost of tickets will opt to stay close to home rather than attend the comparably more expensive performances in the cities. We expect concerns about transportation will be

negatively associated with travel across community boundaries. Lastly, we expect that suburbanites with concerns about familiarity and safety will not be among those who opt to attend performances in the cities, which may be thought of as daunting and dangerous by many suburbanites who are unfamiliar with these areas.

Data

In late 2002 and early 2003, 987 Twin Cities area residents responded to a telephone household survey designed to elicit information about the frequency and pattern of their attendance at live performing arts events (identifying reference). Respondents were contacted by list-assisted random digit dial. Of the working numbers dialed, 79 percent resulted in contacts. Of those contacted, 55 percent cooperated with the request for an interview. Of those cooperating, 94 percent completed the interview.² Nearly one-third of the interviews were completed on the first call, but one took as many as 27 calls to secure an interview. The response rate is a multiplicative function of contact, cooperation, and completion rates ($79*55*94$), which calculates to 41 percent.

We sought a number of respondents in each county proportional to the estimated number of people that lived in each county. We completed 331 and 196 interviews in Hennepin and Ramsey Counties, respectively. Hennepin County is dominated by Minneapolis and Bloomington, and Ramsey County is dominated by St. Paul. Despite the fact that Hennepin County include some suburban, exurban, and even rural areas, our county-level analysis defines Hennepin and Ramsey Counties as central city counties and their 527 survey respondents as central city residents.

We completed 146 interviews in Dakota County, 93 in Anoka County, 62 in Washington County, 35 in Carver County, and 34 in Scott County. We count these 370 survey respondents as suburban residents.

² The 6 percent of organizations that did not complete the interview were “interrupted” during the course of the interview, usually by the interviewee’s unwillingness to continue the interview. Interviewees were not informed at the beginning of the interview that the bulk of the survey questions focused on attitudes toward and attendance to performing arts events, so those who refused at the outset cannot be said to be those who were anti-arts. Only this small percentage of interrupted interviews includes those who may have broken off the interview when they found that they did not enjoy discussing the content. Consequently, the study cannot be said to be greatly biased toward pro-arts respondents.

Differential Attendance Patterns

We asked respondents if they had been to a live professional dance performance in the past 12 months. We asked the same question for opera, play or musical, orchestra, and other live performing arts performances, such as chamber music, jazz, and folk or traditional arts. Table 1 shows the percentage of respondents who said yes to each question, separately for city dwellers and suburbanites. It indicates that a greater percentage of city dwellers attend all kinds of performing arts performances, and that a greater percentage of city dwellers (74 percent) have attended any live performance in the past 12 months than suburbanites (68 percent). The reason for this relationship is likely tied to the proximity of city dwellers to a greater number and array of performance offerings. That is, city dwellers either reside in the city because they want to be close to these offerings, or they are more likely to attend because of the convenience that proximity affords.

[Table 1 here]

With 74 and 68 percent of Twin Cities city dwellers and suburbanites attending a live performing arts event in 2001, 26 percent and 32 percent did not attend such a performance. We label these respondents nonattenders, and they are the first row of Table 2. In addition to asking whether respondents attended a particular type of performing arts performance or not, we also asked them how many times they had attended in the past 12 months. We summed the individual counts to derive an overall number of live performing arts events attended.

We divided attenders into four groups. Infrequent attenders are those who attended one or two events in 2001. While the respondents in this category may have attended any one or two performing arts events that year, their infrequent attendance is likely tied to a religious holiday, a community festival or event, or some other occasion that leads them to attend a performing arts performance. Our break between *casual* and *frequent* attenders is based on the supposition that *frequent* attenders attend performing arts events at least one time per month, which equates to 12

or more events per year. Those who attend less than this, but more often than twice a year, we label as *casual* attenders.

[Table 2 here]

The trends in Table 2 support the assertion that city dwellers were more active in attendance of performing arts events than suburbanites at the time of this study. In addition to having a greater percentage of nonattenders, suburbanites have a greater percentage of infrequent attenders. In contrast, city dwellers have a slightly higher percentage of casual attenders and a notably higher percentage of frequent attenders.

[Tables 3a and 3b here]

Tables 3a and 3b differentiate city dwellers and suburbanites by their attendance and crossing behaviors in different disciplines. City dwellers are most likely to attend only in the city. Theatre attenders show the greatest propensity to cross into the suburbs, with 8 percent of respondents attending in both the suburbs and the city and another 8 percent attending only in the suburbs.

In contrast, suburbanites are most likely to cross into the cities to attend live performing arts performances. Theatre provides the greatest stay-home opportunities for suburban arts attenders, with 12 percent of respondents saying that they attend theatre only in the suburbs. Nonetheless, more than twice this number of respondents exclusively crosses to the city for their theatre fix.

Characteristics of Boundary Crossers

To test the hypotheses, we created a range of variables that measure characteristics of individuals that we expect to be related to boundary crossing behavior. Our models include four different sets of variables. The first set includes *demographic* variables. *Age* is the age of the respondent, in years, at the time of the interview. Values range from 18 to 91. *Education* is an ordered, five category indication of the highest level of education completed by the respondent.

Categories are elementary school, high school (or GED), junior college or technical school, four year college or university, and post-graduate degree. *Income* is an indication of the respondent's household income. Ranges offered are less than \$25,000, \$25,000 to \$50,000, \$50,000 to \$100,000, \$100,000 to \$150,000, and \$150,000 and above. More than 1 in 8 respondents chose not to report their range of household income. Rather than remove these cases from the analysis, we estimated values of income based on age and education level.³

The second set of variables indicates a respondent's attendance to a particular type of performance in the past 12 months. For example, the *dance* variable takes on a value of 0 if the respondent has not attended a dance performance, a value of 1 if the respondent has attended as many as 5 dance performances, and a value of 2 if the respondent has attended more than 5 dance performances. *Theatre* is treated the same way. However, we had too few city dwellers that attended opera performances in the suburbs to create an independent *opera* variable. Therefore, we collapse orchestra and opera attendance into a single *orchestra-opera* variable.

A third set of variables gauges respondent attitudes toward and personal involvement with the performing arts. For *personal attitudes*, we summed the responses to a series of questions about how respondents feel the performing arts affect them personally. Specifically, we asked people the extent to which they believe attending live performing arts is enjoyable to them, is thought provoking, helps them understand other culture better, is primary a social occasion, encourages them to be more creative and makes them feel more connected to the community. Responses to individual questions take on a value of -2 if a respondent strongly disagrees, -1 for disagreement, 0 for neutral opinions, 1 for agreement, and 2 for strong agreement. So, the summed measure of 6 items ranges from -12 to +12 with a 0 value indicating on-balance neutrality on the range of personal value questions.

³ We estimate an equation for household income level based on education level (5 categories), age, and the square of age. The squared term reflects the curvilinear nature of household income, i.e. household incomes increase as its breadwinners age up to a point, but then declines in retirement. All three variables are significant at $p < .001$, and they explain 20 percent of the variation in household income categories. The resulting model is $Y(\text{INCOME}) =$

$-0.47 + 0.21 * \text{EDUCATION} + 0.12 * \text{AGE} - 0.001 * \text{AGE-SQ}$. We use this model to estimate values of household income level for 121 cases that gave their age and education level but refused to report household income. In the models presented in Table 4, we also include a dummy variable that takes on a value of 1 for cases for which we estimated the income level, and 0 otherwise. A significant value of *income estimated dummy* would indicate that income nonrespondents have different boundary crossing behavior than income reporters, a finding that would call into question the wisdom of using the estimated values.

The *community attitudes* measure is created in the same way. However, this measure includes summed responses to eight questions about the perceived role that the performing arts play in the broader community. Specifically, we asked people the extent to which they believe that the performing arts improve the quality of life in the greater Twin Cities area, promote understanding of others and different ways of life, provide opportunities to socialize with other people, are a source of pride for those in the greater Twin Cities area, contribute to the education and development of children, contribute to lifelong learning for adults, help preserve and share cultural heritage, and contribute to the economy of the greater Twin Cities area. The summed measure of 8 items ranges from -16 to +16.

The *personal participation* variable also sums across several items, but the items in this measure are queries about non-live enjoyment of the performing arts or personal participation in artistic activities. Specifically, we asked respondents how often they listen to classical music or opera on CDs, tapes, or radio; play a musical instrument; watch a play, dance, jazz or classical music on television; sing in a choir or singing group; or perform or assist in the production of a performing arts presentation. Respondents received a value of 4 on a particular item if their response was “every day”, a value of 3 for “at least once a week”, a value of 2 for “at least once a month”, a value of 1 for “occasionally”, and a value of 0 for “never”. *Personal Participation* sums the five items, resulting in a measure potentially ranging between 0 and 20, although the highest value in the data is 19.

The fourth set of variables is *barriers* to attendance to performing arts events. We asked respondents the extent to which cost of tickets, difficulty or cost of getting to or parking at events, or that performances are in unsafe or unfamiliar locations are reasons why they do not attend more performing arts events in the greater Twin Cities area. *Cost as barrier*, *transportation as barrier*, and *unsafe/unfamiliar as barrier* take on a value of 3 if an item is cited as a “big reason, a value of 2 if a “moderate reason”, a value of 1 for “a small reason” and a value of 0 for “not a reason at all.”

Models 1 and 2 use only those respondents who live in Hennepin and Ramsey Counties, the city dwellers. The dependent variable in these models is the log-odds that a city dweller attended any performing arts performance in the suburban Twin Cities area in the 12 months

preceding the interview. Model 1 includes the attitude and involvement measures. Since the parameter estimates are small and non-significance, I estimate a second model this set of variables. However, the exclusion of these variables does not greatly influence the parameter estimate. The only substantive change in Model 2 is that city dwellers who voice concerns about the safety or familiarity of the location of performing arts venues are marginally more likely to have attended a performing arts event in the suburbs.

[Table 4 here]

The results indicate that only two variables investigated in this study substantially influence boundary crossing behavior by city dwellers. First, the positive and significant parameter estimate for *Income* indicates that the probability that a city dweller attends performing arts performances in the suburbs increases with household income. Respondents from higher income households are more likely to cross the boundary between central city and suburb. Second, *Theatre* attenders are more likely to cross from the city to the suburbs than people who do not attend theatre. This finding is consistent with the descriptive statistics in Table 3a that indicate that a comparatively high number of central city respondents attend theatrical performances in the suburbs.

Models 3 and 4 are based on respondents who live in the suburban Twin Cities counties. The dependent variable in these models is the log-odds that a suburbanite attended any performing arts performance in the Twin Cities in the 12 months preceding the interview. We already know from Table 3b that a large number of suburbanites trek to the city for performing arts events. These models show which individual characteristics separate those who cross the boundary from those who do not.

The main finding from Models 3 and 4 is that performing arts attenders are more likely to travel from the suburbs to the city than non-performing arts attenders. This finding is hardly earthshattering, given that people who do not attend performing arts are not candidates to cross boundaries at all. However, the findings are still instructive in that all three measures, *dance*, *theatre*, and *orchestra-opera* are positive and significant, indicating that suburbanites see all three offerings as reasons to travel into the central city.

The only other significant relationship in Model 3 and 4, an effect strengthened by the elimination of the attitude and participation measures in Model 4, is that concerns about *cost of tickets* are associated with higher likelihoods that a suburbanite will attend a performing arts event in the central city. This finding is counter-intuitive given that the prevailing costs of tickets downtown are not lower than the prevailing costs of suburban performing arts offerings. However, the finding may indicate that suburbanites feel that the central city performances are more worthy of high ticket prices than performing arts performances in the suburbs.

Discussion

Boundary crossing to attend performing arts events is much more common among suburbanites who seek the greater range and quality of offerings in the central cities. Indeed, suburbanites are more likely to travel into the central cities to attend performing arts events than they are to seek out performing arts events in their own communities.

Individual demographic characteristics play much less role in explaining boundary crossing behavior than we had hypothesized. We argued that younger, more educated, and higher income city dwellers would be more likely to cross boundaries to attend performing arts events with suburbanites who overall better reflect these characteristics. We also suggested that increasing education levels and increasing income levels would be associated with urban boundary crossing by suburbanites. However, the only characteristic that bears out is the positive relationship between household income and boundary crossing by suburbanites. Higher income levels give some city dwellers broader opportunities to sample the cultural offerings around the Twin Cities metropolitan area, as well as the opportunity to join their wealthier suburban colleagues in attending performing arts events as a social occasion. For suburbanites who travel into the city for performing arts events, however, age, education, and household income do not seem to matter. Suburbanites from different demographic groups are equally likely to attend cultural offerings in the central cities.

We also hypothesized that attendance habits by suburbanites would cause them to travel into the cities for particular types of performances, but that attendance of particular performing art forms would not explain why city dwellers would cross into the suburbs for performances.

We appear to be correct on the first count, but not on the second. Consistent with our hypothesis, suburbanites do go to the city for dance, theatre, and live classical music performances. However, theatre attendance *does* seem to be a reason why city dwellers cross to the suburbs. Theatre, the most common live performance offering in the suburbs, is a draw for central city inhabitants.

Additionally, we suggested that positive attitudes about the performing arts and the level of personal participation or enjoyment of the arts via non-live media would be associated with the kinds of people who might cross community boundaries to attend performing arts events. These ideas are not borne out by the data. Models 1 and 3 reveal small and nonsignificant parameter estimates for the *personal attitudes*, *community attitudes*, and *personal participation* measures. Whatever the reasons for boundary crossing to attend performing arts events, broad attitudes toward and involvement with the performing arts are not among them.

Lastly, we advanced the idea that barriers to attendance would give some clues as to which individuals would be more or less willing to cross community boundaries. We argued that suburbanites who say that cost of tickets is a barrier to greater attendance will be among those who do *not* cross into the city to attend performances. We found exactly the opposite. That is, suburbanites who voice concerns about ticket costs are actually *more* likely to attend performing arts offerings in the city. We also argued that the difficulty or cost of getting to or parking at events would deter respondents from crossing boundaries in either direction. We did not find this to be the case, however; concerns about transportation and parking does not explain either suburban respondent attendance at central city events or city respondent attendance at suburban events. Our final argument regards the perception that performance locations are unsafe or unfamiliar. We felt that concerns about safety and familiarity would be directly related to a person's willingness to travel across community boundaries. However, we found that suburbanites with these concerns are no less likely to attend events in the city than suburban respondents who did not voice these concerns. On the other hand, we did find that city dwellers concerned about safety and familiarity are a bit more likely to go to the suburbs for performing arts events.

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Appendices:

Table 1: Attendance at Live Performing Arts Events in the Past 12 Months (2001)

Discipline	Percentage Attending At Least One Performance	
	City Dwellers	Suburbanites
Dance	30%	28%
Opera	8%	4%
Theatre	60%	48%
Orchestra	25%	18%
Other	40%	30%
Any Discipline	74%	68%

Table 2: Frequency of Attendance at Live Performing Arts Events in the Past 12 Months (2001)

Attendance Level	City Dwellers	Suburbanites
Nonattender (0 events)	26%	32%
Infrequent Attender (1-2 events)	23%	27%
Casual Attender (3-11 events)	38%	35%
Frequent Attender (12 or more events)	13%	6%
Total	100%	100%

Table 3a: Attendance of City Dwellers at Performing Arts Events

	Attended in Both City and Suburbs	Attended only in City	Only Crossed to Suburbs	Attended only Outside the TC metro area	Did not attend	
Dance	2%	23%	3%	2%	70%	100%
Opera	0%	7%	0%	1%	92%	100%
Theatre	8%	41%	8%	3%	40%	100%
Orchestra	1%	21%	2%	1%	75%	100%
Other	5%	24%	6%	5%	60%	100%
Any Discipline	22%	43%	6%	3%	26%	100%

Table 3b: Attendance of Suburbanites at Performing Arts Events

	Attended in Both City and Suburbs	Attended only in Suburbs	Only Crossed to City	Attended only Outside the Twin Cities metro area	Did not attend	
Dance	2%	4%	20%	2%	72%	100%
Opera	0%	1%	3%	0%	96%	100%
Theatre	5%	12%	29%	2%	52%	100%
Orchestra	2%	2%	13%	1%	82%	100%
Other	3%	7%	15%	5%	70%	100%
Any Discipline	20%	10%	35%	3%	32%	100%

Table 4: Logistic Regression Models Explaining Boundary Crossing

	City Dwellers, Going to Suburbs		Suburbanites, Going to City	
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Age	.00 (.01)	.00 (.01)	-.02 (.01)	-.02 (.01)
Education	-.12 (.11)	-.10 (.11)	.10 (.15)	.07 (.14)
Income	.49*** (.12)	.49*** (.12)	.06 (.16)	.06 (.16)
Dance	.28 (.21)	.29 (.20)	1.31*** (.38)	1.59*** (.36)
Theatre	.84 *** (.21)	.86*** (.20)	1.90*** (.31)	1.98*** (.30)
Orchestra-Opera	.16 (.21)	.22 (.21)	2.17*** (.52)	2.25*** (.50)
Personal Attitudes	-.00 (.03)		.04 (.04)	
Community Attitudes	.00 (.03)		.05 (.04)	
Personal Participation	.04 (.04)		.02 (.06)	
Cost as Barrier	.13 (.10)	.14 (.10)	.24~ (.13)	.27* (.12)
Transportation as Barrier	.08 (.11)	.08 (.11)	-.08 (.15)	-.01 (.14)
Unsafe/Unfamiliar as Barrier	.20 (.13)	.21~ (.13)	-.18 (.16)	-.18 (.16)
Income Estimated Dummy	.20 (.30)	.22 (.30)	.00 (.45)	-.07 (.45)
Intercept	-3.35*** (.63)	-3.32*** (.58)	-1.98* (.16)	-1.38~ (.76)
N	493	496	339	340
N missing	34	31	31	30

Note: ~ p<.10 * p<.05 ** p<.01 *** p<.001, Standard errors in parentheses levels thereby improving the quality of life.